

Open Science NL

Open Research Software Advisory Panel

Meeting Notes

22 September 2025, 15:00 - 17.00 CEST (UTC + 1:00)

Location: MS Teams

Attendees

- Ana Martinovici
- Daniel S. Katz (until 16.30)
- Daniela Gawehns
- Laurents Sesink (LS)
- Martine de Vos
- Mateusz Kuzak
- Santosh Ilamparuthi
- Thomas Pronk
- Mark van Assem - Acting Co-Chair
- Marta Teperek (MT) - Acting Chair

Apologies

- Morane Gruenpeter
- Vincent Traag
- Maria Cruz

Absent

- Karthik Ram
- John Swinbank

Welcome and agenda

The meeting started at 15.02. Minutes of the last meeting were published on Zenodo:

<https://zenodo.org/records/14592058>

Update on the implementation of the OSNL Work Programme 2024-2025

MT updated the panel on the following developments pertaining to the implementation of the OSNL Work Programme 2024-2025:

- 60 full proposals were submitted in the Open Science Infrastructure call. The committee will meet to assess and prioritise the proposals in October and the Steering Board will decide on the awards in December.
- The deadline for the call for proposals *Research on open science* was on 16 September 2025. 46 proposals were submitted.
- The funding programme for research software sustainability will go ahead and will be awarded to the Netherlands eScience Center.

Update about the “Metaproject” from those who attended the consultation

None of the panel members were present, hence LS shared an update he received from colleagues, complemented by MT, who was updated on this by her colleague:

- In general, the project aims to coordinate developments around open science infrastructures. [The project report has been recently published.](#)
- Criticism: insufficient time for the consultation, the report being available in Dutch only, researchers perspective missing.
- The organisers (UNL and SURF) acknowledged the criticism and assured the group that the project was only in the initial phase and that subsequent developments will be more inclusive. In general, it is challenging to take onboard various and often conflicting perspectives. Lesson learnt is to communicate earlier on the goals, timeline, and when feedback will be requested.

Remarks from panel members:

- The consultation effort did not involve researchers, who are the end users. This is problematic and it limits the possible uptake and risks of developing infrastructure which is not fit-for-purpose.

Confidential: Feedback on the draft OSNL Work Programme 2026 – 2027

Meeting close and plans for the upcoming meeting

In the upcoming panel meeting in December the new work programme will be announced and the plans for the election of new members will have to be discussed.

The meeting ended at 16.39.

Resources shared by panel members

- Data and Software Management Plans must be public and should be machine-readable: [Data and Software Management Plans must be public and should be machine-readable – Daniel S. Katz's blog](#)
- Access to research software: Opportunities and challenges (OECD workshop): [Access to research software: Opportunities and challenges](#)
 - Report will be written up and shared in the coming weeks
- Isager, P. M., van 't Veer, A. E., Freeman, Z., Martinovici, A., Breemer, L., van Ravenzwaaij, D., ... Rasti, S. (2024, July 24). Hackathon proceedings for: Perspectives on Scientific Error–Coordinating Quality Control in Practice. <https://doi.org/10.31222/osf.io/94a6f>
- Gruenpeter, M., Di Cosmo, R., Granger, S., Abramatic, J.-F., Cruse, L., & Martinelli, N. (2025). Software Heritage: Open Science Strategic Blueprint. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17051965>

- National Academies of Sciences et al (2019), "Understanding Reproducibility and Replicability," in Reproducibility and Replicability in Science, National Academies Press (US) (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK547546/>)
- Plesser HE (2018) Reproducibility vs. Replicability: A Brief History of a Confused Terminology. Front. Neuroinform. 11:76. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fninf.2017.00076>